

Level of Practice on Parenting Styles and Emotional Intelligence Development of Tigwahanon Learners

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Index Terms:

parenting styles, emotional intelligence, Tigwahanon learners, child development, socio-emotional learning, indigenous education

Abstract. This study examined Indigenous parenting styles and the development of emotional intelligence among Indigenous learners. Specifically, it assessed parenting styles, namely authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive, and evaluated emotional intelligence across the domains of interpersonal skills, empathetic responses, stress tolerance, optimism, assertiveness, problem-solving, and flexibility. Furthermore, the study investigated the relationship between parenting styles and the development of emotional intelligence among Indigenous learners. This study was conducted at Panuluanan Te Alubihid and Basbasanan To Opis, both extensions of Namnam Integrated School, located in Barangay Namnam, San Fernando, Bukidnon. The school primarily serves Indigenous Peoples (IP) learners belonging to the Tigwahanon tribe. A descriptive-correlational research design was utilized, and data were gathered through validated survey instruments administered to the respondents. Findings revealed that authoritative parenting was highly practiced, authoritarian parenting was moderately practiced, and permissive parenting was practiced to a lesser extent. Indigenous learners demonstrated a high level of emotional intelligence overall, with very high levels in empathetic responses and flexibility, and moderate levels in assertiveness. Correlation analysis showed that overall parenting styles were not statistically significantly related to overall emotional intelligence development. However, authoritative parenting was significantly associated with empathetic responses and problem-solving skills. The study concludes that while authoritative parenting may influence certain emotional intelligence domains, parenting styles as a whole do not significantly determine overall emotional intelligence development in Indigenous learners. Emotional intelligence may also be shaped by broader cultural, community, and environmental factors, as well as social interactions and lived experiences.

Introduction

Education is not just about classroom education. It also assists in developing the emotional, social, and cultural development of learners. Emotional intelligence (EI), or the capacity to comprehend and regulate one's own emotions, express empathy, and build positive relationships, is one aspect of this development. This is because emotional intelligence is not accorded as much attention as academic performance. This is an issue as learners might excel in school, yet still have issues with attitude, behavior, or relationships. Parents contribute significantly in this regard, as they are the first instructors for their children. The parenting style, or how parents guide, care for, and discipline their children, has a significant influence on their children, including the development of emotional intelligence (Olutope et al., 2019).

This research is located in the Indigenous Peoples School (IP School) Extensions of Namnam Integrated School, Brgy. Namnam, San Fernando, Bukidnon, where Panuluanan To Alubihid and Basbasanan To Opis are annexes of Namnam Integrated School. Its members are part of the Tigwahanon tribe, one of the seven known Indigenous Peoples (IPs) of Bukidnon. In this case, the emotional and social development of children is still rooted in traditional parenting practices (Department of Education, 2015). Yet, Indigenous learners have special challenges, including the language barrier, cultural

discrimination, the lack of resources, and the need to reconcile between the traditional identity and mainstream education (Department of Education, 2011).

Other countries have conducted studies demonstrating the influence of parenting styles on Emotional Intelligence. For example, authoritative parenting has been associated with higher EI, whereas authoritarian and permissive parenting styles have been associated with lower EI (Olutope et al., 2019). Studies also indicate that caring parenting is beneficial in building resilience in children and young adults (Kuo et al., 2024). Cultural parenting practices within Indigenous contexts are viewed as protective factors that enhance children's emotional and social abilities (Knauer et al., 2018).

Despite these results, little is known about the impact of Indigenous parenting approaches in the Philippines, particularly among the Tigwahanon tribe in Sitio Alubijid and Sitio Opis, on learners' emotional intelligence. The majority of the available literature focuses on Western or urban settings. Meanwhile, local studies on Indigenous Filipino learners primarily emphasize educational challenges rather than the cultural assets that can facilitate the development of Emotional Intelligence. This study aims to fulfill that need by examining the levels of parenting practices among Tigwahanon families in Panuluanan, To Alubihid, and Basbasanan to Opis, and by examining the relationship between these practices and the development of emotional intelligence in learners. The results can be used to develop culturally sensitive educational approaches that integrate school- and home-based strategies to enhance resilience, empathy, and flexibility among Indigenous students.

This study is grounded in three theories: the Parenting Style Theory (1966) by Baumrind, the Emotional Intelligence Theory (1995) by Goleman, and the Circle of Courage Model (Brendtro, Brokenleg, and Van Bockern, 1990), explaining the relationship between the parenting practices and the process of developing emotional intelligence in learners within Indigenous communities. The combination of these theories is a good basis for the study. The framework by Baumrind describes the impact of parenting style, the theory by Goleman focuses on the dimensions of emotional intelligence, and the Circle of Courage focuses on the cultural strength of Indigenous parenting. The paper integrates these viewpoints to identify the effect of Tigwahanon parenting practices on the emotional intelligence of learners in a distinct setting of IP Schools, namely Panuluanan To Alubihid and Basbasanan To Opis.

Figure 1 presents the study's conceptual framework, illustrating the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The independent variable is the level of practice on parenting styles, which includes authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive parenting. These parenting styles represent the approaches parents use to guide and discipline their children. The dependent variable is the level of emotional intelligence development among indigenous learners, measured through interpersonal skills, empathetic response, stress tolerance, optimism, assertiveness, problem-solving, and flexibility. The framework assumes that parenting styles may influence the development of emotional intelligence in learners.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram showing the relationship between the Independent and Dependent Variables

This study aimed to determine the level of practice of Indigenous parenting styles and their effects on the emotional intelligence of Indigenous learners in Panuluanan To Alubihid, Sitio Alubijid, and Basbasanan To Opis, Sitio Opis, Brgy. Namnam, San Fernando, Bukidnon.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of practice on parenting styles in terms of Authoritative parenting, Authoritarian parenting, and Permissive parenting?
2. What is the level of emotional intelligence development among Indigenous learners in terms of: Interpersonal skills, Empathetic response, Stress tolerance, Optimism, Assertiveness, Problem solving, and Flexibility?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of practice on parenting styles in terms of Authoritative parenting, Authoritarian parenting, and Permissive parenting, and the level of emotional intelligence development among Indigenous learners in terms of: Interpersonal skills, Empathetic response, Stress tolerance, Optimism, Assertiveness, Problem solving, and Flexibility?

Null Hypothesis

The hypothesis will be tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between significant relationship between the level of practice on parenting styles in terms of Authoritative parenting, Authoritarian parenting, and Permissive parenting, and the level of emotional intelligence development among Indigenous learners in terms of: Interpersonal skills, Empathetic response, Stress tolerance, Optimism, Assertiveness, Problem solving, and Flexibility at Panuluanan To Alubihid and Basbasanan To Opis, Namnam IS Extension.

Methodology

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Panuluanan To Alubihid and Basbasanan To Opis, which are extension schools of Namnam Integrated School located in Barangay Namnam, San Fernando, Bukidnon. These schools serve Indigenous learners belonging to the Tigwahanon tribe. Both communities are classified as geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas (GIDA). The schools provide education from kindergarten to Grade 6 and primarily serve Indigenous learners whose upbringing is strongly influenced by traditional cultural practices and community values.

Respondents of the Study

The study respondents included intermediate-level learners (Grades 4, 5, and 6) from the two extension schools and their parents. A total of 112 learner-parent pairs participated in the study. Among these, 28 learners were from Panuluanan To Alubihid and 84 from Basbasanan To Opis.

Sampling Procedure

Complete enumeration was used as the sampling technique. All learners in Grades 4, 5, and 6 from both extension schools, along with their parents, were included in the study. This approach was chosen because the number of eligible respondents was manageable, enabling the study to include all relevant participants.

Research Instrument

Two adapted instruments were used in this study. The Parenting Styles and Dimensions Questionnaire (PSDQ) was used to measure parenting styles, specifically authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive parenting. The Emotional Intelligence Scale, adapted from the Bar-On and Goleman models, was used to measure emotional intelligence in terms of interpersonal skills, empathetic response, stress tolerance, optimism, assertiveness, problem solving, and flexibility.

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to data collection, the researcher secured approval from the Schools Division Office of Bukidnon and the school administration of Namnam Integrated School. Permission was also obtained from the National Commission on Indigenous Peoples (NCIP) following the Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC) process in accordance with the Indigenous Peoples Rights Act of 1997 (RA 8371). After obtaining the necessary approvals, questionnaires were administered to the selected

learners and their parents. Clear instructions were provided to ensure accurate responses while maintaining confidentiality and cultural sensitivity throughout the data collection process.

Scoring Procedure

A. Level of Practiced Parenting Styles

The data obtained from the two instruments should be rated using standardized processes, with appropriate adjustments for the research environment. In the case of the Parenting Styles and Dimensions Questionnaire (PSDQ), parents' responses will be rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 (Never) as the lowest and 5 (Always) as the highest.

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualifying Statement
5	4.20 – 5.00	Always	Very Highly Practiced
4	3.40 – 4.19	Often	Highly Practiced
3	2.60 – 3.39	Sometimes	Moderately Practiced
2	1.80 – 2.59	Rarely	Less Practiced
1	1.00 – 1.79	Never	Not Practiced at all

B. Emotional Intelligence Development of Tigwahanon Learners

The Emotional Intelligence Scale is also scored on a five-point Likert scale: 1 (Strongly Disagree), 2 (Disagree), 3 (Neutral), 4 (Agree), and 5 (Strongly Agree). Scores were categorized by the seven domains of emotional intelligence, and the domain-specific and general average scores were obtained.

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualifying Statement
5	4.20 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Level
4	3.40 – 4.19	Agree	High Level
3	2.60 – 3.39	Neutral	Moderate Level
2	1.80 – 2.59	Disagree	Low Level
1	1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Level

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. The mean and standard deviation were used to determine the levels of parenting styles and emotional intelligence. The Pearson Product–Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was used to assess the relationship between parenting styles and the development of emotional intelligence among Indigenous learners.

Delimitation of the Study

This research focuses only on the level of practice of Indigenous parenting styles and their impact on the development of emotional intelligence among Indigenous learners in Panuluanan To Alubihid and Basbasan To Opis, which are school extensions of Namnam Integrated School, in Sitios Alubid and Opis, Brgy. Namnam, San Fernando, Bukidnon. Three types of parenting styles, including authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive, are the only ones the study measures with the help of the Parenting Styles and Dimensions Questionnaire (PSDQ). Emotional intelligence is assessed across seven dimensions: interpersonal abilities, empathetic reactions, coping with stress, optimism, aggression, problem-solving, and flexibility.

The study's respondents are limited to Indigenous learners at the intermediate level (Grades 4, 5, and 6) and their parents. Other grades and even Indigenous schools and communities not in Panuluanan, To Alubihid, and Basbasanan, To Opis are excluded. Moreover, only the relationship between parenting styles and emotional intelligence is considered in the study. This study does not discuss other potential reasons, such as family income, peer influence, cultural differences, or teacher-student relationships.

Results and Discussion

The analysis and interpretation of the data collected in the study are provided. It presents the level of Indigenous Parenting Styles and Emotional Intelligence Development of Indigenous learners. Means, standard deviations, and Pearson correlation coefficients are used to report results and determine the significance of relationships between variables.

Level of Practice on Parenting Styles

Table 1 shows the levels of practice for parenting styles, including authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive. It presents the mean scores, standard deviations, and qualitative descriptions of the indicators that assess parents' responsiveness, communication, emotional support, discipline, and guidance toward their children. These indicators reflect the different parenting approaches parents use to raise and guide their children within the family environment. The results provide an overview of how frequently these parenting behaviors are practiced and of their potential influence on learners' emotional and social development.

Parenting Style	Mean	SD	QD
Authoritative Parenting	4.41	0.231	Very Highly Practiced
Authoritarian Parenting	2.61	0.267	Moderately Practiced
Permissive Parenting	2.28	0.255	Less Practiced

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualifying Statement
5	4.20 – 5.00	Always	Very Highly Practiced
4	3.40 – 4.19	Often	Highly Practiced
3	2.60 – 3.39	Sometimes	Moderately Practiced
2	1.80 – 2.59	Rarely	Less Practiced
1	1.00 – 1.79	Never	Not Practiced at all

Table 1. Level of Practice on Parenting Styles

Table 1 shows that authoritative parenting was very highly practiced, with an overall mean of 4.41 (SD = 0.231). The highest-rated indicator was encouraging children to talk about their problems (M = 4.52), indicating that parents promote open communication and emotional expression within the family. The lowest indicator was respecting children's opinions and encouraging them to express their views (M = 4.31), although it remained very highly practiced. These results suggest that Tigwahanon parents frequently demonstrate warmth, responsiveness, and supportive guidance toward their children. The findings support Baumrind's Parenting Style Theory (1966), which emphasizes that authoritative parenting promotes emotional competence and positive social behavior among children. However, Authoritarian parenting was less practiced, with an overall mean of 2.61 (SD = 0.267). The highest indicator was the use of physical punishment as a disciplinary method (M = 2.70), interpreted as moderately practiced, while the lowest indicator was the punishment of children by isolating them without explanation (M = 2.47), interpreted as less practiced. These findings indicate that Tigwahanon parents generally avoid harsh or punitive disciplinary approaches and instead prefer supportive and communicative parenting practices. Previous studies have also found that excessive authoritarian parenting may hinder children's emotional expression and development (Trejo & Jannah, 2022). Consequently, permissive parenting was also less practiced, with an overall mean of 2.28 (SD = 0.255). The highest indicator was spoiling the child (M = 2.38), while the lowest indicator was stating punishments without actually enforcing them (M = 2.20), both of which were interpreted as less practiced. These results suggest that Tigwahanon parents are not overly lenient or indulgent. Instead, they maintain appropriate guidance and discipline while still providing warmth and support. This finding aligns with Baumrind's Parenting Style Theory (1966), which suggests that permissive parenting may negatively affect children's self-regulation and emotional development. Overall, the results indicate that Tigwahanon parents predominantly practice authoritative parenting, characterized by warmth, responsiveness, and structured guidance, whereas authoritarian and permissive parenting styles are less common.

Level of Emotional Intelligence Development

Table 2 presents the level of emotional intelligence development among Indigenous learners across seven dimensions: interpersonal skills, empathetic response, stress tolerance, optimism, assertiveness, problem-solving, and flexibility.

Emotional Intelligence Dimension	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Interpersonal Skills	4.12	0.328	High Level
Empathetic Response	4.30	0.336	Very High Level
Stress Tolerance	3.45	0.403	High Level
Optimism	4.19	0.304	High Level
Assertiveness	3.08	0.311	Moderate Level
Problem-Solving	4.15	0.320	High Level
Flexibility	4.35	0.323	Very High Level

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualifying Statement
5	4.20 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Level
4	3.40 – 4.19	Agree	High Level
3	2.60 – 3.39	Neutral	Moderate Level
2	1.80 – 2.59	Disagree	Low Level
1	1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Level

Table 2. Level of Emotional Intelligence Development

The results show that Indigenous learners demonstrated high to very high levels of emotional intelligence in most domains. Flexibility obtained the highest overall mean ($M = 4.35$, $SD = 0.323$), which is interpreted as a Very High Level, indicating that learners are highly adaptable to change and open to new experiences. Empathetic response also recorded a very high level ($M = 4.30$, $SD = 0.336$), suggesting that learners demonstrate strong concern for others and maintain positive interpersonal relationships. These findings reflect the influence of cultural values that emphasize cooperation, belongingness, and collective responsibility in Indigenous communities. Interpersonal skills ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 0.328$), optimism ($M = 4.19$, $SD = 0.304$), and problem-solving ($M = 4.15$, $SD = 0.320$) were rated high, indicating that learners generally demonstrate positive social interaction, resilience in facing challenges, and the ability to analyze situations and make decisions. Stress tolerance also obtained a high level ($M = 3.45$, $SD = 0.403$), suggesting that learners are capable of managing emotional pressures and maintaining composure in stressful situations.

However, assertiveness ($M = 3.08$, $SD = 0.311$) was interpreted as moderate, indicating that learners may still need further development in confidently expressing their thoughts and defending their opinions in social interactions. Overall, these findings indicate that Indigenous learners possess strong emotional and social competencies that support positive interactions and resilience. The results align with Goleman’s Emotional Intelligence Theory (1995), which emphasizes the importance of emotional awareness, empathy, and self-regulation in developing positive social behaviors. Moreover, the findings support the Circle of Courage Model (Brendtro et al., 1990), which highlights belonging, mastery, independence, and generosity as important factors in the positive development of Indigenous youth.

Correlation Analysis

Pearson Product–Moment Correlation was used to examine the relationship between parenting styles and the development of emotional intelligence among Indigenous learners. The analysis assessed whether authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive parenting styles were significantly associated with the different domains of emotional intelligence.

<i>Independent Variable</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Practiced Parenting Style	Emotional Intelligence Development	0.143	.132	No Significant

(correlation is significant if the level of significance(p) (sig 2 tailed) is less than 0.05)

Table 3. Overall Correlation Analysis between the level of practiced parenting styles and the level of Emotional Intelligence Development

The results revealed that authoritative parenting was significantly positively associated with empathetic response ($r = 0.312$, $p < .001$), indicating that higher levels of supportive and responsive parenting were associated with stronger empathy among learners. However, authoritative parenting also showed a weak but significant negative relationship with problem-solving ($r = -0.203$, $p = .032$). The other emotional intelligence domains, including interpersonal skills, stress tolerance, optimism, assertiveness, and flexibility, did not show significant relationships with authoritative parenting. Similarly, authoritarian parenting demonstrated weak relationships with most emotional intelligence domains, with significant but very weak associations observed only for empathetic response and problem-solving. The remaining domains showed no statistically significant relationships. For permissive parenting, the results indicated no significant relationship with any of the emotional intelligence domains. This suggests that permissive parenting practices were not significantly associated with learners’ emotional competencies in this study.

Overall, the correlation analysis showed that parenting styles were not significantly related to the overall development of emotional intelligence in Indigenous learners ($r = 0.143$, $p = .132$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between parenting styles and the development of emotional intelligence was accepted.

These findings suggest that although parenting practices may influence certain emotional competencies, the development of emotional intelligence among Indigenous learners may also be shaped by broader contextual factors, including cultural values, community interactions, and school experiences.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following conclusions were drawn. Indigenous parents predominantly practiced authoritative parenting, characterized by warmth, responsiveness, and structured guidance. This suggests that Indigenous parenting practices emphasize emotional support and constructive discipline rather than harsh or overly permissive approaches. Indigenous learners generally demonstrated a high level of emotional intelligence across most domains, particularly in empathetic response and flexibility. However, assertiveness was found to be only moderate, indicating that while learners are emotionally aware and adaptable, their confidence in expressing themselves may still need further development.

Although certain domain-level relationships were observed between authoritative parenting and specific aspects of emotional intelligence, the overall relationship between parenting styles and emotional intelligence development was not statistically significant. This implies that parenting styles alone may not fully determine the emotional intelligence of Indigenous learners. The development of emotional intelligence may also be influenced by other factors, such as the school environment, peer interactions, cultural practices, and community support.

Future researchers are encouraged to explore additional variables that may contribute to the development of emotional intelligence and to conduct studies involving larger, more diverse populations of Indigenous learners to gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing their emotional and social development.

Ethical Consideration

This study carefully adhered to ethical principles throughout the research, particularly regarding the involvement of Indigenous Peoples (IPs) and children as participants. Informed consent was obtained from the parents or guardians prior to data collection, and assent was obtained from the learners. The participants were informed about the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, the voluntary nature of their participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty.

The anonymity and confidentiality of the responses were ensured by using codes instead of names, and all data were secured in password-protected files accessible only to the researcher. No identifiable information was used in the study. Cultural sensitivity was also observed to ensure that the research instruments and procedures respected the values, traditions, and language of the Tigwahanon community. The study followed the ethical guidelines of the Department of Education (DepEd) and the National Commission on Indigenous Peoples (NCIP) for conducting research in Indigenous communities.

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing does not apply to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

References

- Agbaria, Q., Mahamid, F., & Veronese, G. (2021). The association between attachment patterns and parenting styles with emotion regulation among Palestinian preschoolers. *SAGE Open*, 11(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244021989624>
- Alavi, M., Salehi, M., & Bahrami, F. (2020). Parenting style, family cohesion, and emotional intelligence as predictors of stress tolerance in adolescents. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 29(4), 1012–1025.
- Arenas, R., Carlos, J., Chua, C., Maceda, E., & Arcinas, J. (2022). Authoritarian mothering experiences of top-performing senior high school students in the Philippines: Impact on psychological, emotional, and social health. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 3(7), 1165–1175. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.03.07.17>
- Aydın, B., & Yıldız, M. A. (2020). The relationship between emotional intelligence, interpersonal skills, and optimism in Turkish adolescents. *Journal of Educational Sciences Research*, 10(2), 78–95.
- Brendtro, L., Brokenleg, M., & Van Bockern, S. (1990). Reclaiming youth at risk: Our hope for the future. National Educational Service.
- Department of Education. (2011). National Indigenous Peoples education policy framework (DepEd Order No. 62, s. 2011). Department of Education.
- Department of Education. (2015). Indigenous Peoples education curriculum framework (DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2015). Department of Education.
- Depon, M., Pelino, R., Pilapil, J., & Villanueva, K. (2024). Parenting style and emotional intelligence among late adolescents in psychology students at Bestlink College of the Philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Education*, 12(2), 34–45.
- EAS Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies. (2021). Parenting style and social skills developed among the senior high school Grade 12 students in Zone IV, Schools Division of Zambales. *EAS Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies*, 3(2), 65–71. <https://doi.org/10.36349/easjhcs.2021.v03i02.002>
- Eisenberg, N., Spinrad, T. L., & Morris, A. S. (2020). Parental socialization of emotion and children's emotional development. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 71, 541–566. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-010419-050915>
- Fadhila, R., & Rinaldi, D. (2022). Parenting styles and their impact on the emotional intelligence of adolescents at SMKN 1 Padang. *Journal of Educational Trends*, 11(4), 67–75.
- García Linares, M. C., Cerezo, M. T., & de la Torre, M. J. (2018). Parenting styles and their influence on adolescents' emotional intelligence and academic achievement. *Psicothema*, 30(1), 64–70. <https://doi.org/10.7334/psicothema2017.205>
- Knauer, H. A., Ozer, E. J., Dow, W., & Fernald, L. C. H. (2018). Stimulating parenting practices in Indigenous and non-Indigenous Mexican communities. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(1), 29. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15010029>
- Kuo, C.-H., Lin, T.-H., Chen, Y.-C., Suen, M.-W., & Ni'matuzahroh. (2024). Correlation among parenting styles, resilience, and socioeconomic status in college students' emotional intelligence. *KnE Social Sciences*, 9(5), 636–646. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v9i5.15207>
- Laghari, M. I., Nawaz, M., Ishtiaq, M., & Bushra, S. (2024). Impact of parenting style on academic achievement, emotional intelligence, and self-esteem among university students in Southern Punjab. *Journal of Psychology Research*, 10(1), 56–70.
- Lestari, W., Rusmana, A., Rahmianti, E., & Saripah, I. (2022). Unraveling emotional intelligence: Exploring parenting patterns and sociodemographic determinants. *Al-Ishlah: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 14(3), 3171–3183. <https://doi.org/10.35445/alishlah.v14i3.7037>
- Olutope, A. E., Akpunne, B. C., & Olajide, O. A. (2019). Parenting style, emotional intelligence, and psychological health of Nigerian children. *Asian Journal of Pediatric Research*, 2(2), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajpr/2019/v2i230100>
- Sharma, P., & Yadava, R. (2025). Parenting styles, locus of control, and emotional intelligence among young adults. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 13(1), 1–12.
- Trejo, M., & Jannah, R. (2022). The association between parenting styles and emotional intelligence in early childhood. *Child Development Journal*, 5(2), 112–120. <https://doi.org/10.53905/ChildDev.v1i01.4>

Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.